

Supplementary Materials: Behavioral strategies of prehistoric and historic children from dental microwear texture analysis

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Table S2: Values for the microwear signatures for the sample

Table S2a: Neandertal

Specimen	Tooth	<i>epLsar</i>	<i>Asfc</i>	<i>Smc</i>	<i>HAsfc9</i>	<i>HAsfc81</i>
El Castillo 924	ULdi1	0.0186	1.74	2.98	0.19	0.33
El Sidrón SD1721	URdc	0.0181	4.67	3.93	0.15	0.35
Engis 2	ULdi1	0.0173	1.12	20.52	0.3	0.81
Krapina_13	LLdi2	0.0166	0.96	6.84	0.46	0.98
LaChaise_S 14-2	LRdi1	0.0179	1.44	8.72	0.36	0.82
LaChaise_S 14-3	LRdi2	0.0187	0.87	442.1	1.11	1.02
LaChaiseB D_BD19	LRdc	0.019	4.88	448.1	0.53	1.49
Pech del'Aze_1	URdi1	0.016	1.7	63.2	0.57	1.39

Table S2b: Early Modern Humans

Specimen	Tooth	<i>epLsar</i>	<i>Asfc</i>	<i>Smc</i>	<i>HAsfc9</i>	<i>HAsfc81</i>
Qafzeh_10	ULdc	0.0177	1.91	76.84	0.6	3.53
Qafzeh_4	URdc	0.0173	0.78	6.46	0.77	0.91

Pavlov_13	di	0.0166	0.88	5.18	0.59	0.7
Pavlov_14	dc	0.0181	0.82	6.77	0.44	0.75
Pavlov_16	di	0.0171	0.74	3.93	0.22	0.45
Pavlov_18	di	0.0169	2.79	19.98	0.28	0.74
Saint Germain_19 70-7-4	di	0.0173	0.5	5.02	0.21	0.51
Saint Germain_19 70-7-8	dc	0.0171	0.82	5.15	0.1	0.37
Solutre	LRdi2	0.0163	1.11	15.14	0.55	1.03
Saint Germain_B 3	LLdc	0.0175	0.93	3.93	0.2	0.5
Espinoso Nicho 3 #43	LRdi2	0.017	2.21	2.98	0.23	0.35
Abrigo de la Castañera#1 33	ULdc	0.017	1.16	3.93	0.69	0.76
Abrigo de la Castañera #198	URdc	0.0179	3.03	2.98	0.4	0.41
Mazo #200	Ul dc	0.0168	2.59	2.98	0.36	0.42

Table S2c: Recent Modern Humans Amarna

Specimen	Tooth	<i>epLsar</i>	<i>Asfc</i>	<i>Smc</i>	<i>HAsfc9</i>	<i>HAsfc81</i>
Amarna_Eg ypt_SK11	Ldc	0.0167	3.14	5.13	0.26	0.66

Amarna_Eg ypt_SK195	Rdi1	0.0166	1.37	9.04	0.64	1.11
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK198	Ldi1	0.0192	2.97	5.09	0.67	1.18
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK199	Ldc	0.0167	1.64	8.6	0.3	0.59
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK242	Rdi2	0.0158	1.95	8.93	0.61	1.22
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK243	Rdi1	0.0161	1.26	6.84	0.24	0.39
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK244	Ldi1	0.0171	1.05	3.93	0.21	0.43
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK258	Rdi1	0.0168	1.72	20.8	0.44	0.84
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK272	Rdc	0.0165	2.59	15.75	0.39	0.88
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK274	Rdc	0.0171	1.7	5.18	0.39	0.67
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK312	Rdi1	0.0172	2.22	6.84	0.42	0.86
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK330	Rdi2	0.0176	1.67	6.84	0.24	0.38
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Amarna_Eg ypt_I192	Ldc	0.0152	3.15	11.93	0.47	1.27
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Amarna_Eg ypt_I373	Ldc	0.0162	1.08	5.02	0.22	0.42
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK304	Ldi1	0.0149	3.62	5.11	0.4	0.97
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK284	Rdi1	0.0177	17.99	4.11	0.24	0.83
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Amarna_Eg ypt_SK197	Rdi1	0.0182	6.12	11.74	0.64	1.49
Amarna_Eg ypt_SK196	Rdi1	0.0168	4.75	9.04	0.93	1.1
Amarna_Eg ypt_SK238	Ldi1	0.0176	3.65	6.81	1.01	1.41

Table S2d: Recent modern Humans Point Hope

Specimen	Tooth	<i>epLsar</i>	<i>Asfc</i>	<i>Smc</i>	<i>HAsfc9</i>	<i>HAsfc81</i>
Ipiutak_Poi ntHope_83	URdi1	0.0137	1.27	3.84	0.49	0.76
Ipiutak_Poi ntHope_108	ULdi1	0.0157	1.13	6.62	0.45	0.66
Ipiutak_Poi ntHope_167	URdi1	0.0175	1.95	9.04	0.18	0.65
Tigara_Poin tHope_244	URdi1	0.0183	1.41	11.93	0.58	1.14
Tigara_Poin tHope_273	URdi1	0.0187	2.89	3.93	0.47	0.82
Tigara_Poin tHope_280	URdi1	0.0179	0.85	3.93	0.21	0.42